

The Rise and Fall of the Urban Environmental Products on Pleasure Basis

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to discuss different aspects of human-product interactions in urban environment as a design problem in relation to “pleasure” issue. The aspirations, capacities, limitations and present activities of “urbano-Man” in a designed space are going to be examined and his objective and subjective value systems are going to be redefined in order to find out means of providing user satisfaction by a “pleasurable-city” life.

The quantity of artificial products, so called “urban artifacts”, in the environment will inevitably increase, in relation to several factors such as; population growth, political and social change, various types of transportation and continually improving technology. Therefore, the importance of any man-machine interface becomes more significant increasingly in the urban environment. Designers as always face various challenges and opportunities in creating brand-new services and techno-machines with attractive visual characters making the city more pleasurable and habitable.

This paper tries to provide designers with information on how subjective value systems of people living in communities could be materialized via urban environmental design in order to render the city an area of shared values with pleasurable living spaces contributing to proper public democracy. The object defines the “value system” of urbano-Man into account. It is clear that the subjective values of man as images, values and objectives are never entirely static things. A backward-looking or even static view of any culture is therefore, a highly mischievous occupation but it has also vital importance. It is also fact that these value systems are precious possessions for design to develop an understanding of any dynamic design model. Finally, the study explores the extent to which basis and capabilities should be detected throughout the “pleasurability” in public spaces for achieving a safer and a better urbano-life.

Keywords: open-spaces and user behaviour, urban pleasure, city identity and hidden culture, street furniture, alienation, vandalism.

Problem

Meeting the environmental needs of Man is the main intention of environmental design. This generally means furnishing and equipping the city in keeping with what people want. The core objective of the environmental study is to identify and clearly define possible directions for interdisciplinary work connecting design and social sciences regarding the conception, production, construction and use of objects for ever-increasing the quality of physical environment and communications.

Urban environmental design has become the art of dealing with artificial. In fact, the urban environment has now turned out to be more synthetic than even be less so than tomorrow, for better or for worse, hundreds of products yet-to-be designed will make up the urban pattern. In recent years, the design discipline has developed from the restricted concentration on the

design objects, environments and communications towards an expansion of its field to include the design of processes, services, structures and systems in creation and promotion of creative ideas and principles. Most such “innovative products” are indispensable to providing a better public environment for expanding populations. The attention paid to designed objects and “brand- new” product contexts in the street help to advance the image of the city, its aesthetic values and its buildings. Designers and industry have the great confront and opportunity to create new services and machines of attractive visual character that will make the “city” more **pleasurable** and **habitable**. On the other hand; the density of products in the urban environment will inevitably increase, depending on the effect of several forces, such as; population growth, political and social needs, transportation and technology. The city has become a jungle of post and products and many signs and symbols struggle for user attention. Yet, when viewed comprehensively, they produce more and more visual congestion than signals. The human organism has had to adapt to these contaminants, which pollute the visual spaces.

What is required! Is the imaginative analysis of both environmental needs and wants, followed by dynamic design articulation of Urbano –Man . In sum, to a series of creative or innovative activities that could be defined as design of the contexts within which traditional design methods and classical design operations. These new contexts involve the critical consideration of social, cultural, economic, technical and environmental concerns.

All citizens use public spaces or “open spaces” and they have their special experiences and expectations with in the contributions for a good public democracy. User participation and satisfaction is also one of the vital aspects of the decision making process regarding environmental design issues. Environmental designers have always worked along the tie lines of social and behavioral scientists and sensitized the Urbano-Man ; his expectation, feeling and general behavior. Designer must use a precise procession of procedures to order the new environment, so as to appeal to the human activities and daily performance in the public spaces.

Differentiation of Value System of Urbano-Man

One of the crucial point in urban environmental design is, how the value system of Urbano-Man will be satisfied in near future. A useful way of classifying different aspect of this value

system is driven on the space, activity, performance and product relations of the user in the public environments. The methodology of urban environment designing is now a system, which is a set of interrelated rules and principles that structure the physical and conceptual theme of the city. This systematic ordering has one of fundamental objective to physical environment and which may be called the *quantitative aspects* of user's adaptability. The subjective value systems of man are the behavioral orientation of Man in the urban environment as values; images, information and knowledge also can be named as *qualitative aspects* of his adaptability. The quantitative aspects of his adaptability are centered on the conduct of studies involving the measurement of human performance in his capacities and limits.

Quantitative information or objective system values of urbano-Man are free from the cultural differences. If they are more static and have various scientific outputs, understanding of man-machine system equation, and tend to look at user capabilities and limitations of adaptability are required. Traditional human-factors approaches are very often with physical aspects of any consumer within product use such as their cognitive and physical abilities. These sorts of issues might be thought of as physical needs of user or physiological need pleasures. If they are handled well in the product design, the user may feel relieved at the absence of problems or may simply not notice.

The qualitative information covers the psychology, environmental perception and cross-cultural data about urbano-Man. The quantitative information provides data from design, ergonomics and perception dealing with in the framework of behavioral orientation and physical adaptation of user. It is obvious that the subjective value system of urbano-Man as images, values and objectives are never entirely static things. They have invariable state of change and appear to be changing at cross-cultural differences. A backward-looking or even static view of culture is therefore, a highly mischievous occupation, but it has vital importance. It also fact that the subjective value systems of urbano-Man are precious possessions for environmental issues to develop an understanding of the dynamic models and analysis of dynamic changes must always be taken into consideration by urban environmental designers.

The pleasurable city as a well-built or man-made environment is the organization space, time meaning and communication. Rapoport argues that while the physical components of all

cities are quite the same, it is the nature of meaning and underlying principles of their organizations and relationship which differ, as well associated behavior and these need to be analyzed, so that the generalizations and comparisons may be made (Rapaport 1982). The further discussion on Man's adaptability in terms of his behavioral orientation and physical adaptation can be finalized by classification of his physical and moral values which are both affected by man-environment interface system under different circumstances. In spite of difficulties in differentiating the areas of disciplines, such classification must be made in order to have systematic study, which as follows;

i) The objective value system of Man is the limit of his performance in adaptation to the physical environment. These may also be called the quantitative aspect of his adaptability.

ii) The subjective value system is the behavioral orientation of Man in the urban environment, environmental perception as values, images, pleasure information and knowledge also can be driven as qualitative aspect of his adaptability.

Meaning of man-made environment

The study focuses on the subjective value system from now on and it states that; there are always limits and barrier to any kind of adaptability or degree of satisfaction which is one of the most intense topics of discussion in whole of man-environment interface. Yet, there exists common view that there is no unlimited adaptability and that a man-made environment based on such an assumption will be costly in long term even if definition of results are not obviously clear. (Dubos 1965) The price of "adaptation" might not be immediately evident or easily observed but that must be carefully sought out. The most crucial point in the adaptation and satisfaction is the question of the "price to be paid". Subjective part of man-environment studies are concerned with the systematic study of mutual interaction of people and their man-made environment.

These studies are multi-disciplinary studies they are differing from traditional design approaches. It also concerned with is the effect of the built environment "defined space" on human behavior, mood or well-being .It is important to note that "pleasure" (mood, well-being, degree of satisfaction, the condition of consciousness, sensation induced by the enjoyment, participation level) with man-made environment or products accrues from the

relationship between a user and a product or depends on the hidden interaction in between (Jordan 2000). Any man-made environment effects are generally mediated by a filter system in this interaction. They are a part of “perceived environment” and they involve expectations, motivations, decisions and symbolic meaning which are based on the sub-value system of the any user .It is also implies that built environments have some cues for behavior and the environment can, therefore be seen as a form of non-verbal interaction by using the distinction between fixed feature space (*walls, doors, etc*), semi fixed feature space elements” (*furniture, furnishing, etc.*) and non-fixed feature elements (*people, decoration, gestures and so on*) . These are traditional subjects of non-verbal communication studies. If the design environment is seen as a process of encoding information, then the user can be seen as decode it. If the codes are not shared, not understood or inappropriate, than the environment does not communicate (Hall 1970).

Using these approaches, it is possible to discriminate between the direct and indirect effects of the man-made environment. The former are those where the environment directly affects the general behavior, mood, satisfaction, pleasure, performance and over all interaction. The latter are those in which the environment is used to draw conclusion about social standing or status of its occupants and their behavior, which are modified accordingly. Finally; if there is a mutual interaction between the people and environment, then there must be some links or mechanisms, which interact as follows;

- i) Environment as a form of non verbal communication on a subjective bases,
- ii) Environment as a symbol system,
- iii) Environmental perception and cognition are seen to be important mechanism which are given meaning to it,
- iv) Environment is closely link to culture, where people match their cultural characteristics as values, expectations, norms, pleasure and behaviors.

The obvious mainstream between man and his environment does not clearly state that and actually exist; furthermore, the physical aspects of environment are not standing apart from the multi-dimensional context in which man has.

User Attributes in Environmental Design

Man is the key term in the study of urban environmental design and understanding of his values, aspirations and reactive power is the primary interest of designers. The goal of the city builder is to understand and synthesize these systems as need as aspirations of the client group. How does the city builder or municipality best serve the community needs? How can a designer ensure that the end product is culturally acceptable and pleasurable? These are important issues for those people who are working in the environmental design professions. In most of the retrospective studies, the end product does not share the values and images of man in the street means. The complexity and heterogeneity of the target group is admitted and when designers realizes that culture is never static, it has a uniform state of change to some out cut, the designer-is an agent to changes (Moughtin 1992). The lack of feed back from consumer to manufacturer (citizen to municipality) contributes to the perpetuation of inadequate urban environmental-product on the public right-of-way. Malt (1989) declares that, it is not the public compliance in the face of environmental stupidity symptomatic of emperor's-clothes syndrome, in which no one wants to be first to acknowledge the situation's absurdity? Perhaps, the consumer has not seen any other ways. He may be victim of "municipal mystique". He may assume that there are no ways to make his daily environment look better and to provide him more pleasurable, safe, amenity and comfort. Because of municipal charm, the public is blocked to think about objects in the environment as fixed as static rather than looking for need to solutions in which can take new and different forms at different times to satisfy the local conditions. Therefore, people have not questioned the quality and ability of their public products and "hedonic benefits" of all these items are not recognized. The characteristics of the user profile that always work within the product are somehow diminished and never discussed in the urban environmental equipment design context. Street clutter and ugliness have not been improved because there was not political need to acknowledge that the public places belong to the people.

This condition is in evolution now the consumer is becoming more active attuned to the confusion and ugliness of the environment and urban environmental design-equipments through public opinion in media, TV, press editorials and graphics. This is the way of the conversion of the passive to active participation of consumer who has began to realize that it is his money, that is being spent for public improvement and pleasure. Soon he will learn to articulate his needs. The city resident will force purchasing changes by using the various techniques of participation and illustration of his voting power. Moughtin (1992) claims that

another reason for the present public antipathy towards the recent urban development lie squarely with training of the architects and planners .He also adds that the large extent of architects, urban designers and planners have been pre-trained in a synthetic atmosphere where the subject has been skilled with a little or no reference to the public value system whom the most of the product is intended. Education in a crystal-house in the recent past has been dominated by blustering of novel, but empirically interested.

Community Identity and Open Spaces

Man naturally depends on external stimuli, thus the shape of his environment and for this reason he forms a creative propensity and his identity. This is not needed primarily for artistic or intent activities. It assist man for instance, in the making development and shaping of his personality, in the process of decision making and finding solutions for everyday problems. Another vital problem in many cities is the lack of community identity and values sufficient to induce a sense of belonging or caring. The problem is not so much shabbiness of the city as its lack of vitality and dilution of enjoyment. Most of cases, people in the street have not questioned the quality and utility of their identity. Besides, lack of feedback from consumer to the manufacturer contributes to perpetuation of inadequate urban equipment on the right of way. In reality, the consumer is the man in the street. He never meets variety o goods for comparison-shopping and he can not exercises the traditional veto of the market place.

All citizens use public open spaces. The space is “open” only when it is publicly accessible. Urban products and amenities are public goods in a technical sense and thus they are hard to allocate in normal private markets, yet they are easily destroyed by over-consumption and production of negative externalities. The high density of products in urban environment is one of the major causes of visual pollution, noise and unsightliness. The design elements, which are perceived in the public realm, are thus in a position to stimulate a feeling of well - being or uneasy and those persons who are responsible as an instrument for humanizing the environment must see their individual layout and design. Users are basically all the inhabitants of a city, ranging from small children to elderly people. They have their special experiences and expectations.

Public spaces are important features of the landscape of everyday life. Empirical researches, historical analysis and some demonstration projects indicate that the highest degree of human

satisfaction with various activities should be realized on the democratic open spaces and it can be play an important role in shaping the public culture.

Man-Made Environment

The ultimate job of design is to transform man's environment and tools, by extension, to man itself. An over-technological, sterile human environment has become one possible future. The fact is the streetscape now is more synthetic than yesterday and even less than tomorrow.

HELLMAN (1970)

Figure 1.

No longer grass and trees make the connecting between man and his environment. Nine out of ten cities will soon be contained with a totally manufacturing envelope (Malt 1989). For better or for worse, streets, sidewalks, traffic signs and symbols, mailboxes, telephone units, light poles and various of products, yet under-designed will make up the urban pattern and they must be assembled from the consumer point of view. In the near future, the man-product relations will totally be depended on the man-machine interaction in the urban environment and the task is to use technology in a more pleasurable and habitable way (Gursu 1996). In any pre-industrial village there were no traffic, no control signs, no identification labels, no street- lights, furniture and information centers. Once up on a time; people know each other, the rules of life were clear and the form of the environment was direct physical expression of those rules (fig 1). Today, people are strangers in their cities. They do not know and cannot see how things work. Users, support systems, the vast networks of government, production, commerce, transportation, communication, education, health services, power, water waste disposal, law enforcement are remote. The information supplied in the environment is largely irritable both users immediate purposes and to general understanding of the environment in which they live in. For the foreseeable future, unpredictable alienation of the user must be considered (Gursu 1990).

A visual survey at any urban street reveals the extent to which many different products are repetitively required for communication for control of pedestrian and motorist. The great number of devices is required for lighting, security information and amenity. Presently, most products on the public right of way are highly specialized, and each one allowed performing only one function. The *single function product-oriented design approach* inevitably makes vast overlapping and duplication of materials and cost. This causes a high order product density unfortunately, which has low order of management and control. These inefficiencies must be paid for one way or another. If the city and its population were static, they might have been possible to diminish the clutter and inefficiency by re-designing individual items. But in dynamic circumstances, if there is an excess population in the city it self, there will be an urgent need for systematic increment of the products. The real problem is not the density of a product; significantly it is the way in which density is organized. The amount of public investment in urban environment will enhance with the several forces at work due to following (Gursu and Akman 1989).

- i) There is the demand spurred by population,
- ii) Political and social need to rebuild and overhaul,
- iii) Affluence as expressed by vote's approval of increase expenditures,
- iv) Technological improvements,
- v) Services and Marketing.

Mass production of urban components are indispensable to the goal of providing a better public environment for intensifying population in a way that new services and technology of attractive visual framework that will make the "city" more **pleasurable** and **habitable**.

The products of industry are inescapable; in the street at work when at play, they form tangible reality of our lives to extent that they have become an axiom to speak of man-made world. These transform always manage to survive in the urbano-Man's world in the form of simultaneous and incompatible demands for continuity and enhancement the superiority of daily life. We are in a period of social change; never before have witnessed change at today's pace and also admit that the cities have grown by happenstance, without plan or order in frantic rush to meet the commercial and residential demand as rural explored into mighty manufacturing nations. Yet many prominent figures still say that the most important feature of an urban atmosphere should be "enduring value's" which is infrequently defined, and it is worth younger generations questioning. Nevertheless, as with the corporate identity, the change to improve the community identity does not require rejection of continuity.

Connection to the past and the sense of perspective sharpen the user sensitivity and past identity, when they set out to approve or reject the new. Change must be determined, with the values substituted when shown to be superior to the old. It is also a fact that through conservation and heritage the city and its identity can be more meaningful. This questioning of the society's values by the public transcends the usual alienation of the younger generation from the older. At this time in the history of the cities a disaffection with the environment exist among most age groups, as well as racial and economic strata. But in any event in much of the society there is an emerging attack on values based on materialism, which results in "things". Then, what are the most valid criteria for consumer appeal in this dynamic social content?

The alteration of cities within the acceptable limits can only be achieved by means of massive resources and production capability of industry. Because of both quality and quantity, industry will inevitably assume a more dominant role in shaping our environment.

Conclusion

The fact is the cityscape is now more synthetic than yesterday and may be less so than tomorrow. The urban environmental design has become the art of dealing with artificial and as a result of technology and science, the machines is a replacing muscle as a way of life. It is now commonplace to think of the rise of machines as aids to perceive and manipulate and make the environment more pleasurable and enjoyable and so the city has become a man-made synthetic organism, which structured and framed within the system's components. The urban community can be looked upon as a complex system of the related functional activities directed toward meeting all needs of users. The important values of function for every individual are the standard of living, housing, working, well being, recreation and support for the first three. The user intention as always works on the line of the action space and its surroundings. The user also examines the quality of the environment with its reflections on his value system and he compares it with the ideal. The quality and taste of the user interactive environment becomes more important than the overall quality of the geographical ones. The better environmental products such as signs, traffic control systems and effective street lighting are much more important than the city's overall identity whereas the alienation of Urbano-Man existed in social and the environmental context.

Today, as people associate more closely with their environment, they have begun to realize that it is their money, which spent for public improvements and pleasure. For this reasons, the bureaucracy must required planning and rebuilding objectives for reaching the design standards that provide consumer satisfaction, comfort and pleasure. Another vital problem in many cities is lack of community identity and values sufficient to induce a sense of belonging or caring. The problem is not so meanness of the city as its lack of strength and intensity of enjoyment. Urban form is defined as a physical expression of culture. It is also related directly to the user satisfaction and ultimately to the public participation in design process.

Through the concept of supportive environment and through the argument about evolutionary aspects, it is suggested that any cultural preposition that exist for an activity in a given space will usually be greatly supported by appropriate design means. It also suggests that the urban environment as a system of settings for system of activities which are combined with all human considerations. They provide a framework for cities that would be much more varied,

complex, interesting, supportive and hence more satisfactory. It is also fact that the range of urban environmental products has changed and extended as a result of the dynamic changes in the activities and necessities. Hundreds of products yet un-designed will make up the urban pattern, and that must be assembled from the consumer point-of view. The elements of man-made environment must provide potential within which people perform activities. The urban environmental product theme should ideally form a part of an overall urban design concept that gives consistency and legibility to the city identity.

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